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Open Technologies for Inclusive Educational Delivery at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria: Panacea for Sustainable Development Goal (SDG)

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Abstract

This Paper X-rays Open Technologies for Inclusive Educational Delivery at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria: Panacea for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It has been established that, Sustainable Development Goals, especially, Goal-4 aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all and it is a known fact that, education is a fundamental human right and is critical in achieving meaningful development of any Nation's socio-economics development While, the term inclusive education is when all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that would enable them to meet success in their learning process. Based on the fore-going, the paper discussed the concepts of sustainable development goals, which is seen as the blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all. Similarly, it highlighted inclusive educational delivery with the uses of open technologies at secondary school level of education. The paper further unveiled taxonomies of Open Technologies available for inclusive education at secondary school level such as Artificial Intelligence & open source tool and Learning Analytics & open source tool. Additionally, it examined the advantages of using open technologies for teaching, which include: Flexibility, Scalability and Reliability. Lastly, Theoretical Frame work supporting the use of open technologies for inclusive educational delivery in secondary schools were discussed. Then, Conclusion & Recommendations were made and such recommendation include: That, the quality of support for learners with diverse challenges to cater for diverse needs should be available and usable.

Keywords: Open Technology, Inclusive Education, Secondary School & Sustainable Development Goals

Introduction

Over the years it has been re-emphasized that education must be the top priority for governments and this is so because the global technological revolution is driving rapid and irreversible changes in every area of our lives: new types of knowledge, new forms of communication, new workplace skills. Therefore, harnessing these changes, making the revolution work for everyone, is the key to economic prosperity and the central challenge for progressive politics. There are brilliant examples of technology used to deliver quality education and this include providing the best resources for teachers to use in classroom teaching and home learning; accurate and timely feedback to students; and engaging, collaborative learning experiences adapted for learners' ability with or without disability, It was based on this background that, the most recent edition of National Policy of Education (NPE-2014-Six-Edition) categorically stated that, in section one of the sub-component eight, clearly stated that, in order to fully realized the goals of education in Nigeria and gain from the contributions to the national economy, government shall take necessary measure to ensure that; i- Educational activities shall be learner centred for maximum self-development and self-fulfillment and secondly, Teaching shall be practical, activity based, experiential and Information & Technology Supported (IT). Therefore, the above showcase that effective inclusive education delivery out rightly anchored on selecting and integrating appropriate technology to support implementation process (NPE-2014-Six-Edition; Tony, 2021). Therefore, in a broader perspective, technology can help educators create blended learning environments and leverage on digital technologies and or open technology for formative and summative assessments, bringing new models for learning and teaching to classrooms. This is so because technology in education and the right devices in students' hands helps prepare them with the career and technical skills, they need to be successful today and in tomorrow's workforce. The promise of contemporary technology lives in what these tools can do that previous learning and educational technologies could not and this is for the fact that they are open, connected, and flexible. Therefore, Open Technology, is a concept that encompasses notions of Open Standards, Open Source, and Open Software. (Dinesh et, al;2021). A standard is a specification for a technology or methodology. An open standard is such a specification that is publically available, in such a way that anyone who wants, can obtain it and use it to create an implementation of the specified technology or methodology. Software is open source if its source code is available to the general public without restrictions that limit studying it, changing it, or improving upon it. In

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legal terms, open software is published under an Open-Source license. The “open” adjective is also proudly presented in a host of software projects, some of significant prominence in their field: Open BSD, Open GL, Open LDAP, OpenOffice.org, Open PGP, and so on (Dinesh et, al;2021; Wehler, 2018)

However, open Technology thrives and feeds on Open Standards and Open Source, and is better characterized as a process and attitude similar to the scientific process than by technological aspects. Openness has a vital influence on security and reduces costs by leveling the playing field for product selection, and helps battle inflexibility and legacy-problems (Source) It was in line with the foregoing that, open technology was conceptualized as a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their use. Open technology standards foster innovation while ensuring that devices and networks can work together seamlessly, this collaborative approach to technology development depends upon what the technology intended to be applied for and used to achieving certain objective (s) Hence, open technology is a term that can refers to a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their used and this is possible through open source technology tools. These open-source technologies are seen as the production and development philosophy of allowing end users and developers to not only see the source code of software, but modify it as well for their intended use and accomplishment. The term equally “open-source technology tools” implied also a more generally to a community-based approach to creating any intellectual property (such as software) via open collaboration, inclusiveness, transparency, and frequent public updates (Dinesh et. al., 2021; Wehler, 2018)

There are two terms that largely explained open technology tool and these include open sources and open standard the former “open source” refers to something people can modify and share because its design is publicly accessible and it originated in the context of software development to designate a specific approach to creating computer programs. Today, however, "open source" designates a broader set of values what we call "the open-source way” Open-source projects, products, or initiatives embrace and celebrate principles of open exchange, collaborative participation, rapid prototyping, transparency, meritocracy, and community-oriented development. That open-source software is software with source code that anyone can inspect, modify, and enhance."Source code" is the part of software that most computer users don't ever see; it's the code computer programmers can manipulate to change how a piece of software a "program" or "application" works. Programmers who have access to a computer program's source code can improve that program by adding features to it or fixing parts that don't always work correctly. This therefore, implies Open source and open standards are not the same thing. Because in Open source we mean strictly, that software whose source code is freely available to users for reference, debugging, modification, and/or extension. While, Open standards are, typically, specifications and formal descriptions of software or software interfaces. (Dinesh, et. al., 2021; Wehler, 2018)

More explicitly, standard is a specification for a technology or methodology and open standard is such a specification that is publically available, in such a way that anyone who wants to can obtain it and use it to create an implementation of the specified technology or methodology. A particular product can, by definition, never be a standard; calling a product a standard is a basic category mistake. While not a standard in itself, it can however of course be an implementation of a standard. For software systems, a particular implementation, often called a reference implementation in this case, can play a role in the definition of a standard. As extensively advocated by Richard Stallman. On the Internet for example, interoperability between the vast hordes of connected systems, consisting of many different makes and models of systems running a Mind bogglingly vast arsenal of different software and software versions, is achieved on the basis of the so-called Internet Standards: standards ratified by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) after a process of extensive peer review An example of an open standard is Postel's ‘Transmission Control Protocol that defines TCP, which is the very mechanism used by high-level protocols such as SMTP (mail transfer, which is of course yet another open standard and HTTP (data transfer on the world wide web (Dinesh,,;et, al;2021; Wehler, 2018))

Following this development, Open-source technology is seen has been beneficial to programmers and non-programmers this is because early inventors built much of the Internet itself on open-source technologies like the Linux operating system and the Apache Web server application anyone using the Internet today benefits from open-source software. Every time computer users view web pages, check email, chat with friends, stream music online, or play multiplayer video games, their computers, mobile phones, or gaming consoles connect to a global network of computers using open-source software to route and transmit their data to the "local" devices they have in front of them. The computers that do all this important work are typically located in faraway places that users don't actually see or can't physically access—which is why some people call these computers "remote computers." More and more, people rely on remote computers when performing tasks, they might otherwise perform on their local devices. For example, they may use online word processing, email management, and image editing software that they don't install and run on their personal computers. Instead, they simply access

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these programs on remote computers by using a Web browser or mobile phone application. When they do this, they're engaged in "remote computing. (Dinesh et, al;2021; Wehler,2018)

In this perspective, it is worthy to note that, Sustainable Development Goal 4 ultimately aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and it was an established fact that, education is a fundamental human right and is critical to achieving sustainable development and this so because the United Nations promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Based on this premises it is important to unveil scholar's opinions as regards inclusive or inclusiveness of educational provision. The term Inclusive Education is when all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that enable them to meet success in the core curriculum. This therefore means inclusive education pre-supposes an educational setting that cater for and take care of all learners irrespecful of any disability or inability that they might have but they meet equal treatment and opportunity in a learning centre (Classroom). Hence, it can be seen as an education that includes everyone, regardless of their ability, disability, language, or background, in the same classrooms and schools. It aims to provide equal opportunities, celebrate diversity, and foster a sense of belonging among all students. It also means that the education system must adapt to the needs and strengths of each student, rather than expecting them to fit into a standard model. Similarly, it can be perceived as avenue where all students, regardless of any challenges they may have, are placed in age-appropriate general education classes that are in their own neighborhood schools to receive high-quality instruction, interventions, and supports that enable them to meet success in the core curriculum (Al-Shammari,2019B: Côte-Real, et al:2017: Gandomi, & Haider 2015)

The school and classroom operate on the premise that students with disabilities are as fundamentally competent as students without disabilities. Therefore, all students can be full participants in their classrooms and in the local school community. Much of the movement is related to legislation that students receive their education in the least restrictive environment (LRE). This means they are with their peers without disabilities to the maximum degree possible, with general education the placement of first choice for all students (Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019). Successful inclusive education happens primarily through accepting, understanding, and attending to student differences and diversity, which can include physical, cognitive, academic, social, and emotional. This is not to say that students *never* need to spend time out of regular education classes, because sometimes they do for a very particular purpose for instance, for speech or occupational therapy. But the goal is this should be the exception. The driving principle is to make all students feel welcomed, appropriately challenged, and supported in their learning efforts. (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019; and Mr. Dinesh, et, al; 2021)

Meaning and Conceptualization of Open Technology and Inclusive Education at Secondary School Level

Open Technology as a concept thrives and feeds on Open Standards and Open Source as earlier explained though, it is better characterized as a process and attitude similar to the scientific process than by technological aspects. (Dinesh, et al., 2021) Openness has a vital influence on security and reduces costs by leveling the playing field for product selection, and helps battle inflexibility and legacy-problems. It was in line with the foregoing that, open technology was conceptualized as a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their use.(Wehler, 2018) Open technology standards foster innovation while ensuring that devices and networks can work together seamlessly, this collaborative approach to technology development depends upon what the technology intended to be applied for and used in achieving certain objective (s) Hence, open technology is a term that can refers to a government policy that allows users access to platforms or systems with very few constraints or restrictions on their used and this is possible through open source technology tools. () These open-source technologies are seen as the production and development philosophy of allowing end users and developers to not only see the source code of software, but modify it as well for their intended use and accomplishment. More so, open-source technology tools implied more generally to a community-based approach to creating any intellectual property (such as software) via open collaboration, inclusiveness, transparency, and frequent public updates (Dinesh, et al;2021; Wehler, 2018)

In the same lane, the concept of inclusion has also been extended to the educational field, where it refers to the idea that all students are ensured with equal opportunities; thus, one of the target objectives to be reached by today's school systems has become that of offering the same level of education to all pupils, irrespective of their varying abilities/possibilities. With this understanding, Inclusive education refers to the placement of students with special educational needs in mainstream settings, along with other students without disabilities (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019) Inclusive education determines appropriate educational practices used in general education schools by offering a variety of educational services to help all students with special needs best learn according to their abilities and needs (Al-Shammari,2019A;

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Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019) defines inclusive education as a philosophy that brings stakeholders together to create a school environment based on acceptance and belonging within the school and the community. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has played an influential role in the consolidation of the idea of inclusive education for children with special educational needs in schools. Inclusive education has been adopted to ensure the quality of and right to education for all learners and is now a contemporary educational approach recognized globally. (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019; and Mr. Dinesh, et, al; 2021)

Uses of Open Technologies as Effective Strategies for Inclusiveness at Secondary School Level

Scholars' have identified different methods and strategies that ought to be considered in order to bring about inclusiveness in teaching & learning of disable learners and these inclusive teaching strategies refer to any number of teaching approaches that address the needs of students with a variety of backgrounds, learning modalities, and abilities in secondary school system of education. These strategies contribute to an overall inclusive learning environment in which all students perceive to be valued and able to succeed. The following identified below are some of the evidence-based strategies aim to provide secondary school teachers' teachers with an overview of inclusive teaching practices to support the inclusion of students with a diverse range of abilities and strengths. Many of these strategies are relevant for all students, while others could be relevant to some students and they include ensuring the following as identified by these scholars: (Al-Shammari,2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene,2019).

The Strategies for Inclusiveness in Secondary School Level

1. Keep activities and instructions short, clear and engaging
2. Consider how tasks can be tailored to different student goals, strengths, abilities and learning profiles
3. Provide a visual schedule
4. Prepare students for an upcoming transition
5. Provide a sensitive environment
6. Provide encouragement and guide learning
7. Provide a quiet area
8. Express positive regard and support
9. Facilitate student voice, autonomy and independence
10. Set clear classroom expectations
11. Provide lots of opportunities for students to engage in collaborative learning
12. Teach peers how to interact with each other
13. Support students to manage and self-regulate their emotions among others

The identified above can help learners from secondary school level to be focus and learn with ease. Similarly, major frequent breaks in activities appropriate for a given content may also help to provide concrete examples to suffice and enable them learn better such as simplified text, visual supports, breaking tasks into smaller components, using a variety of teaching strategies, and providing alternate ways for students to respond as feedback for reinforcement and motivation are some of the ways that the listed above can be achieved. Visual cues (such as schedules or cue cards) can let students in secondary school level know what is coming up, and how they should move from one activity to another. learners who find moving from one activity to another challenging will be better prepared if they are aware, it is a coming up activity More so, to provide reminders about upcoming transitions, such as visual supports, countdown timers or regular reminders are indeed very necessary. .it is equally, important to provide an environment that is sensitive to the needs of students who have experienced trauma or adverse childhood experiences and considering providing effective, actionable feedback immediately when students are learning a task. (Al-Shammari,2019B: Côte-Real, et al:2017: Gandomi, & Haider 2015)

Some of the examples of their uses for inclusiveness in teaching and learning at secondary school

1. learning community using Google Docs; Piazza & Q and A Community (Inscribe) This can help to foster an inclusive learning community among secondary school learners. Without guidance, students will often choose friends or peers like themselves for creating informal and formal learning communities. There are several tools available to help create more inclusive learning communities by providing opportunities for students to communicate with the teacher and each other. Just using these tools will not ensure inclusion, however. The teacher needs to provide structure to learning activities and establishing heterogeneous groups; determining group roles that rotate among members; structuring assignments to require

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- interaction and inclusion of diverse perspectives; actively inviting, validating, and using all students' voices; etc. (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019);
2. Secondly, it can help build a community where students of secondary school rely on each other for answers to class-related questions. They are equally an online problem-solving platform that allow them to post questions (including anonymously), answer questions posted by others, see instructor notes about answers, and see which answers have been endorsed by the teacher. Students can also post images, videos, and/or equations using the built-in LaTeX editor, and edit computer code collaboratively. It's a great way for students to recognize the value and contributions of classmates with whom they may not have ordinarily meet before (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019);
 3. Thirdly, it enables creating of groups for Formal and Informal Learning: This strategy can be used to create regular interaction which can go a long way to helping students reach across cultural differences and learn to value those with different identities and backgrounds. Structuring these interactions to promote inclusion of all students is more vital than ever during remote learning. This could be possible with group projects, letting groups self-form can leave some students on the margins. Consider tools that let you organize heterogeneous groups around strengths and interests. This can be with the use of surveys in Canvas or Qualtrics to ask about important characteristics, while more comprehensive teamwork programs like CATME which is available for that. Moreover, students/learners can be encouraged to use Zoom to create virtual study groups. Consider helping them learn to structure those meetings, maybe by having teaching assistants host a few review sessions first. Hosting the first few meetings may also make the groups more inclusive of all class members than might happen in self-formed study groups. These live study meetings can supplement other approaches like crowd-sourced notes or study guides in Google Docs or class Q&As occurring in Piazza or InScribe. (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Dangiliena, & Kloviene, 2019)

Specific open technologies tools for inclusive education delivery to achieve sustainable development goal (SDG) in secondary school level

It has been revealed that one in five 15-year-olds secondary school children lack minimum proficiency in Reading, Mathematics or Science at this level. (UN 2023 SDG Summit) Hence, there is the need to find cost-effective ways of delivering education of a consistently high standard to hundreds of millions of students and the scale of the challenge, already exacerbated by Covid-19 that was experienced couples of years back, this will only grow in the next decade as the world moves towards achieving UN's Sustainable Development Goal 4 in realising inclusive and equitable quality education for all. The solution lies in developing a radically better approach to evaluating and applying new technologies in our educational process (Eleni & Lanitis, 2023)

In line with the foregoing, the end justifications for the use of any technology in teaching and learning process is to ensure democratization of knowledge and as well ensure effectiveness & efficiency in learning process with the technology integration especially, for those educationally challenge learners whom have one form of disability or the other. It was in realization of this fact, that scholars identified the following open technologies tools that could be used to bring about inclusiveness in the educational delivery of disable learners: In the view of Eleni & Lanitis (2023) they identified the following as Open Technologies Tools usable at secondary school level for educational purposes:

1. Artificial Intelligence & open-source tool
2. Learning Analytics & open-source tool
3. Big data & analytics and open-source tool
4. Cloud Computing & Open-source tools
5. Full stack development & Open-source tool

Artificial intelligence at secondary school level of education

Artificial intelligence is one of the most discussed topics in the educational industry. Artificial intelligence in education is a significant technology which helps education in a number of ways. Personalized learning is one of the most important area of education that has used artificial intelligence. In personalized learning, AI helps learners to find the best course material based on ones' identity, interests and way of learning. Artificial intelligence replaced the old-fashioned classroom study with a more personalized and student-centered approach. Artificial intelligence can monitor overall performance by identifying the strength and weakness of a learner. It can rank learners based on their performance and give real-time suggestions to improve the overall performance of their studies. Artificial intelligence is very important so as to keep track, report and monitor the performance of the learners. Chen et al. (2022)

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The term “Artificial Intelligence” (AI) was first mentioned by John McCarthy in 1956 and refers to the ability of computer systems to undertake human tasks (like learning and thinking) that frequently can only be attained through human intelligence. Since the 1970s, the specific field of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) has begun to influence the application of technology to instruction and learning, to improve the learning process, and promote student achievements. The aim of AIED is to establish AI-powered systems such as virtual pedagogical agents, AI robots and intelligent systems which allow flexible, engaging and personalized learning as well as to automate daily tasks of teaching (e.g. feedback and assessment). AI has been extensively used in education in different forms such as computer programs, humanoid robots, web-based chatbots, and online platforms. Chen et al. (2022) indicates the usefulness of AI in education, which may be used in the form of intelligent tutoring systems for special education, natural language processing, educational robots, performance prediction, discourse analysis, teaching evaluation, learner emotion detection and personalized learning. (AlFarsi et al., 2021). (Sadiku et al., 2021). (Southgate et al., 2019).

Learning analytics at secondary school level of education

It was established that learning analytics provides great potential to promote inclusiveness in terms of reducing discrimination, increasing retention among disadvantaged students, and validating particular learning designs for marginalized groups in secondary school or outside it. This open technology it's often assumed in education that its benefits are distributed, that everyone has equal chances of succeeding and that the educational ecosystem is, per se, value and power-free. One of the dominant beliefs is that all learners can succeed if they try hard enough, show grit and resilience and take control of their learning and opportunities (Reed & Jeremiah, 2017; Warren & Hale, 2020).

The definition of learning analytics was established in 2011 and is generally accepted to be the measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their contexts, for purposes of understanding and optimizing learning and the environments in which it occurs (UN 2023 SDG Summit)

As learning is transitioning towards being digital and datafiled, student data from digital learning environments can provide stakeholders (students, instructors, administrators, student centres, among others.) with actionable information (Khalil et al., 2018). That is, it has the potential to facilitate the design and implementation of more appropriate and effective learning pedagogies, empower active learning, identify factors impacting student success at secondary school level, and support the design of courses to meet students' individual needs (Samuelsen et al., 2019; Nguyen, Tuunanen, Gardner & Sheridan, 2021).

Cloud computing as open-source tool at secondary school level of education

The cloud has had a huge impact on the way we use the internet and organize our online lives over recent years, and is one of the most fast-developing aspects of digital technology. It affects home and work life, and is also revolutionizing online learning in school system. The impact on those with special educational needs especially in secondary school level can be even more significant. Therefore, some of the tool that can be use is a virtualized desktop from a basic laptop, PC or tablet, and this can access all the educational resources they need, from any location. This means that being of limited mobility, or having other disabilities that restrict the ability to attend school are no longer barriers to achieving a full education and excelling academically. The tool equally can provide greater and more flexible learning opportunities to everyone, regardless of their age, sex, wealth or social demographic. The use of cloud technology in secondary school would also ensure that this inclusivity also extends to those with special educational needs. It can empower children with visual, learning, age- related, mobility, hearing and speech disabilities to learn more effectively, engage and collaborate with others more easily, and express themselves more clearly. (UNESCO; 2021; ISO, 2012; Mir Ali, 2017; & G3ict, 2023)

Big data analytics and open technology tool at secondary school level of education

Researchers have proven beyond reasonable doubt that, in this era of technological applications and its use for teaching and learning, more especially at secondary school level, in dealing with learners with disabilities which demand all-inclusiveness, Big-data-analytics is one of the open-source tools that can be of immense use and this is because, the Teaching-Learning process is changing significantly due to new technological changes. The adoption of Big Data Analytics in the education sector will enables it to strengthen further and reform the system. Therefore, simply put analytics is defined as a body of knowledge consisting of research techniques in mathematics, statistics, and operations; data collection and storage; techniques of artificial intelligence like deep learning algorithms and machine learning; and big data technologies such as

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Spark, Hadoop, and Hive. In areas where such data or information is stored, analytics is instrumental. Analytics deployment is critical to differentiated services and developing new competitive strategies. (Dagiliene and Kloviene, 2019; Manyika et al., 2011; Corte-Real et al., 2017)

Advantages around the uses of Open Technologies for learning at secondary school level of Education

Researches have shown that creating inclusive classes can help learners improve their performance by enhancing their learning this implies a key starting point for inclusion is making sure everyone feels like they *belong* to the class community where they have opportunities to be heard and engage with classmates. As an effective teacher at secondary school level and with the opportunity of having access to open technologies for learning it is obvious to note that this opportunity has the following advantages for their application and used in secondary school setting as thus:

1. **Flexibility:** The biggest benefit of open technology source in secondary school is that it offers great flexibility to use the platform according to learners needs. Interoperability and connectivity with the existing infrastructure or the platform is easier to attain and it also offers the liberty to the users to make changes to its features.
2. **Reliability:** Open technology source is always under continuous review, which leads to more reliability of the platform. Programs like Apache, DNS, HTML and Perl have proven to be robust and reliable even under strict conditions. Since developers devote their time and expertise, it is updated frequently and various features get added to it from time to time in order to suit different learning needs of the children with diverse learning challenges
3. **Quality:** A software platform of open technology was developed by countless users usually aimed to improve the quality of student learning
4. **Support options:** Open source is usually available for free and it has a huge community group to support the piece of software. The community works together and creates various learning resources and modules suitable for teaching and learning at secondary school system
5. **Support collaborative learning:** Open technologies ensured and provides opportunity for students to engage and collaborates with each other during teaching & learning process. This is a unique advantage to create avenue for peer-to-peer support in learning with any kind of this technology
6. **Ensure learning anywhere any time:** In the current technological dispensation, students' learning is not expected to be through only the conventional means. Hence, open technology used for teaching and learning in secondary school breaks away from this method and allows for students' engagements anywhere, anytime

Challenges and Inhibiting factors associated with open technologies uses for inclusive learning at secondary school level of education

Inclusive education has been enacted from a rights-based philosophy, implementation which requires a change in the mindset of school principals and teachers. Although, in overall, teachers are said to support inclusion, the inclusion of different groups of children, especially those with social, emotional or behavioral difficulties, continues to be considered as problematic and which teachers are expected to managed. However, there could be some perennial challenges that could possibly affecting true success of children with disability and learning in secondary school. They can include the following:

1. Classroom teacher demand to fully support teaching and learning process at this level
2. The quality of support for students with diverse learning disability in secondary school system
3. The degree of knowledge, understanding, and expertise required by classroom teachers in secondary school level
4. The uncertainty and time-consuming nature of identifying different approaches when providing support in secondary school level
5. Poor infrastructural ICT facilities needed in secondary schools to translate related curriculum content of learners with special needs during lesson
6. Gaps in skill and competency of special class teachers in handling technology for teaching & learning at secondary school level
7. There is a shortage of computers, tablets and other devices for conducting electronic lessons and homework. For inclusiveness in learning for an inclusive classroom

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Theoretical Frame work supporting the use of open technologies for inclusive education

In the perspectives of Ertmer & Newby, (2013), noted that, learning theories provide curriculum designers with instructional strategies and techniques verified to facilitate learning in classrooms, which includes the need to implement inclusive education practices for students with special educational needs, especially in general education settings. These instructional strategies and techniques include modifications of curricula and instructional design, the development of structures, and the use of evidence-based practices. Three major theories are considered to underpin inclusive education theory. Effective inclusive education practices should incorporate ideas from each of these theories so that teachers can successfully make curricular and instructional decisions for each student. These theories are identified as: Behaviourism, Cognitivism, Constructivism. The foremost theory, behaviorisms-based inclusive education practices include the application of behaviourism in inclusive education settings, which clearly appears in the emphasis on student behaviour and performance in manipulating stimulus materials (Ertmer & Newby, 2013). Examples of behaviourism-based inclusive education practices are included in well-known instructional approaches such as explicit or direct instruction (Al-Shammari, 2019A; Steele, 2005). Theoretically, behaviourism is one of the classical theories of learning and also recognized as the oldest. Behaviorism is known as a predominant psychological model as suggested by the metaphor for, ‘learning as the acquisition of stimulus-response pairs. Behaviourists ‘believe the objective of the theory is to impart to the learner the knowledge of reality Behaviourism occurs when consequences are associated with the stimulus or response that is followed by reinforcement to be maintained. To summarize, the key principles of behaviourism that support education are: behaviour is learned, behaviour is governed by the setting in which it occurs, teaching does not occur without learning, learning equates to changing behaviour, behaviour is governed by what follows actions, and there needs to be a focus on the observable. While, Cognitivism-based inclusive education practices are specifically the applications of cognitivism in inclusion settings, which involves the emphasis on mental information processing and interactions to guide student learning. And lastly, Constructivism-based inclusive education practices emphasize making learning more meaningful and using real-life experiences. (Abramson, (2013; Akpan, & Beard 2016; Al-Shammari, 2019A)

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to stressed that, Inclusive Education is an on-going, long-lasting process that needs to be pursued with determination, despite the significant challenges it poses; all the available/ suitable means should be employed, including technological tools that are widely recognized as having high potential to help in achieving SDG-Goals, with particular reference to goal-4 which is to be fully achieved by 2030 of the new targets. Therefore, the used of open technologies to deliver effective curriculum for inclusive learning at secondary school system will be a mirage without integrating the right type of technology this is so because of the promise of contemporary technology lives in what these tools can do that previous learning and educational technologies could not meaning they are open, connected, individualizing, free accessibility, flexible to be modified to suite a given learning content of a special needs and above all free to be use with no cost implications

Recommendation

The following recommendations are made for more effective uses of open technologies tools for inclusiveness in the classroom setting of children with disability as thus:

1. Classroom teacher demands, in relation to curriculum interpretation with special need learners should be viable and achievable
2. The quality of support for learners with diverse challenges to cater for diverse needs should be available
3. The degree of knowledge, understanding, and expertise required by classroom teachers should be gauged as been appropriate for learners with disability
4. The uncertainty and time-consuming nature of identifying different approaches when providing support, should be resolved
5. Needed infrastructural ICT facilities needed in schools to translate related curriculum content of learners with special needs during lesson should be ensured
6. Gaps in skill and competency of special class teachers in handling technology for teaching & learning should be taking care of through training and re-training programme

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